

The BAND: a cloud-based virtual desktop for bioimage analysis

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Abstract

Summary

To address the challenges of doing interactive bioimage analysis in a cloud environment, we built the Bioimage ANalysis Desktop (BAND), a cloud-based platform that integrates many bioimage analysis tools into a single virtual desktop environment accessible in a web browser. Each BAND desktop runs as a cluster job with configurable resources including GPUs and each application within a desktop runs as a Singularity container. Several GPU-enabled image visualisation and analysis applications are available in BAND.

Availability and implementation

Deployment code is available at <https://git.embl.de/grp-cbbcs/create-band>.

Installation instructions can be found in the project's wiki at

<https://git.embl.de/grp-cbbcs/create-band/-/wikis/home>.

The BAND is accessible online at <https://band.embl.de>.

Introduction

Bioimage analysis workflows often require extensive human interventions combined with the use of multiple software tools. To deal with human-in-the-loop workflows, bioimage analysis software typically includes a graphical user interface and is often deployed on dedicated desktop workstations. Recently, the combination of increasing data size with the use of more computationally expensive processing methods (e.g. deep learning) has pushed many workflows beyond the capacity of local workstations. Moving such workflows to high-performance computing clusters (HPC) is challenging because HPC often have poor support for interactive tools. A frequent response to this issue is to use large cloud-based virtual machines equipped with remote desktop software leaving users with the task of replicating their local computer environment in the cloud. However, deployment and interoperability of commonly used image analysis software tools in remote environments represent a significant hurdle for most scientists and bioimaging facilities. In particular, setting up a compute environment to make use of specialised hardware such as GPUs either locally or remotely is often a challenging task in particular when different tools have conflicting or incompatible requirements. Attempts at tackling these issues tend to

rely on the deployment of computational notebooks (e.g. ZeroCostDL4Mic, von Chamier et al., 2021) or the development of new dedicated web-based platforms and interfaces (e.g. IMACEL, Shimahara et al., 2019; ImJoy, Ouyang et al., 2019). While these solutions address the cloud deployment problem, they lack interoperability with other imaging tools, have limited data access options and require users to become familiar with a new environment which could limit uptake. Human-in-the-loop workflows are offered by the Galaxy platform (ref) where so-called Galaxy Interactive Tools can be included in a workflow. Table 1 gives an overview of the capabilities of publicly available platforms.

Here we present the Bioimage ANALysis Desktop (BAND), an alternative approach based on a Desktop-as-a-Service (DaaS) platform that aims at making it easier to perform interactive image analysis tasks in the cloud with tools users are already familiar with.

Implementation and features

The BAND builds on components originally developed for the Australian MASSIVE facility (Goscinski et al., 2014), in particular the Strudel (Scientific Remote Desktop Launcher) framework (<https://github.com/monash-merc/strudel-docker-public>). This framework allows creation of graphical desktop-sharing VNC servers as cluster jobs and provides web-based access to the desktops.

The BAND is built on an Openstack (<https://www.openstack.org/>) cloud. We have taken the Infrastructure-as-Code approach using Ansible to provision the entire BAND environment and thus ensuring its overall consistency, scalability and availability. All the servers are provisioned using the HEAT orchestration template (https://docs.openstack.org/heat/rocky/template_guide/hot_guide.html). The BAND system is a 3-tier architecture with a web layer, an authentication layer and a persistence layer, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The BAND system architecture

The BAND currently supports authentication via Google and the upcoming LifeScience AAI (Linden et al., 2021) with the OAuth2 protocol. Keycloak is used to provide user federation to an LDAP server, carry out a custom user access flow and bring up Single-Sign-on/out service across different identity providers. A custom Python script is used to read user attributes from the authentication token and create user accounts in the LDAP server. All the users in the LDAP server are then synchronised to all backend cluster nodes via the SSSD software.

The web layer of the BAND includes a standard AngularJS web application served through the NGINX web server and Strudel APIs and Guacamole client served via an Apache Tomcat container. Communication between the web layer and the backend cluster in the persistence layer is handled by the Strudel API. The web application defines the compute nodes specifications, such as amount of RAM, number of CPUs and GPU and submit them as a VNC batch job. Guacamole renders everything back into HTML5 and displays the desktop environment within the user's web browser.

The desktop environment is a standard Mate desktop. Each software application within the desktop is constructed into its own Singularity container which allows interoperability and reusability of the software by isolating each piece of software and its dependencies. BAND can thus offer multiple versions of the same software and software with normally incompatible dependencies. This is in contrast to more common virtual desktop containers that include all applications and the desktop in a single container which doesn't solve issues with dependencies and in our experience often results in performance issues. The supported software applications currently available within the desktop environment are categorised into four groups: Image analysis, Programming, Data access and other applications that come with the default Mate desktop. The Image analysis group contains Cellprofiler, ilastik, Fiji, Napari, QuPath, DeepLabCut, Cellpose, TissUUmaps and ChimeraX. The Programming group consists of Matlab, RStudio, KNIME and several GPU-enabled JupyterLab instances with different deep learning kernels (e.g. tensorflow, pytorch). Applications that have the capability are configured to make use of available GPUs. The Data Access group includes the XNAT desktop client, the ownCloud client, Rclone, the Aspera client and a custom tool (based on s3fs) to mount S3-compatible object storage via FUSE. The persistence layer contains a standard Slurm cluster, a NFS server, a GlusterFS cluster, pre-built Singularity containers and an auto-scaling script. The NFS server supplies persistent data storage for users' home directories and pre-defined Singularity containers. The data in users' home directories is automatically mounted on demand to all cluster nodes via autofs. The Slurm cluster is made up of two partitions, one for CPU only nodes and one for GPU nodes. Jobs are allocated to nodes according to the user's specifications. A TigerVNC server is pre-installed onto each cluster node which generates visualisation of the desktop environment. The auto-scaling function is carried out by a bash script which scales the cluster automatically based on node availability by invoking the Openstack API and Ansible commands for provision and deletion of nodes. Of note, on GPU nodes, one GPU is reserved for rendering while the others can be used for computation.

One advantage of this setup is that it allows users to configure the compute resources they need for their work. Currently, configurable resources include number

of CPUs, number of GPUs and amount of RAM. In addition, it allows more experienced users to access the underlying HPC environment via Slurm commands.

Data access

Most software used to process bioimages can only do I/O operations on files. This creates a challenge for accessing remote data in a cloud environment. To address this, the BAND provides several utilities to support file transfer using different protocols. In the first one, S3-compatible storage can be accessed via the pre-installed aforementioned client to present buckets and their content as directories and files on the local filesystem. We anticipate that image data access from remote object storage will be significantly improved with the development and adoption of OME-NGFF, a new bioimage data format designed for use in the cloud (Moore et al, 2021) and some BAND applications (e.g. Fiji, Napari) already have functionalities to read image files in this new format directly from S3 buckets. Although we aim for S3 to be the primary means of data access, we're aware that S3-compatible object storage is currently not widely adopted for bioimage data. Therefore other modes of data access are available to allow users to stage their data on the associated GlusterFS filesystem. BAND allows communication (via the WebDAV protocol) with various file sharing services allowing for example access to ownCloud/Nextcloud-based file-hosting services such as EUDAT's B2DROP service (<https://www.eudat.eu/catalogue/b2drop>), Google drive or Dropbox. Files can also be transferred to the BAND using the FTP protocol with the FileZilla application or using the FASP protocol with the Aspera client. Finally we note that for projects repeatedly producing large image data sets, it may be more practical to deploy the BAND close to the data, ideally in the same data centre to avoid or minimise data movement. The Infrastructure-as-code approach we have taken greatly facilitates this.

Use cases

Figure 2: Screenshot of open source image analysis software *ilastik* (Berg et al., 2019) running on BAND. Forthcoming new *ilastik* workflow “Trainable Domain Adaptation” (Matskevych et al., 2022) where pixel predictions from a shallow pixel classifier for mitochondria (blue and yellow) are enhanced with a network, pre-trained on this task (red) and served via the Bioimage Model Zoo (Ouyang et al. 2022 (preprint)). The workflow is interactively adapted by adding annotations for the shallow classifier (blue and yellow lines). Computations for the shallow pixel classifier are performed on CPU whereas calculations for the neural network run on the GPU. This workflow is (at the time of writing) not yet available in any binary *ilastik* release and was deployed on BAND for a tutorial.

The BAND has been successfully used for many courses, including but not limited to, Advances in cryo-electron microscopy and 3D image processing (<https://www.embl.org/about/info/course-and-conference-office/events/cry22-01/>), Deep learning for image analysis (<https://www.embl.org/about/info/course-and-conference-office/events/mac22-01/>), Switzerland's Image and Data Analysis School (<https://2022.zidas.org/>), Current methods in Cell Biology (<https://www.embl.org/about/info/course-and-conference-office/events/cbb22-01/>), NEUBIAS Academy & EOSC-Life - Defragmentation Training School 2022 (<https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/events/neubias-academy--eosc-life---defragmentation-training-school--2022/>) and many more. Each course has a unique requirement for computing resources, and various bioimage software was used to create bioimage analysis workflows during these courses. In particular, *ilastik* was a highly demanded bioimage software in many courses.

Conclusion

We have deployed the BAND, a cloud-based virtual desktop environment to perform interactive image analysis experiments. The modular container architecture allows easy expansion by addition of new software as needed. By providing a familiar environment, the BAND eliminates most hurdles bioimage analysts may face when moving their work to remote resources. In particular users appreciate the no-hassle access to GPU-enabled software and for this reason, the BAND has already been used to run several practical courses on image analysis and deep learning.

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